

USE OF APPS SUCH AS KAHOOT AND IBRAT ACADEMY FOR LEARNING GRAMMAR

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Annotation: Using online platforms to learn grammar is a newly introduced approach in the EFL area in Uzbekistan. Tools like Kahoot and Ibrat Academy can provide interactive and game-based learning experiences that help students engage with grammatical rules in innovative ways. These platforms allow students to practice grammar through quizzes, games, and different learning methods. This paper analyzes the advantages, difficulties, and instructional approaches related to using these platforms for learning grammar.

Keywords: grammar, online platforms, Kahoot, Ibrat Academy, game-based learning, testing, interactive learning.

Annotatsiya: Grammatikani o'rganishda onlayn platformalardan foydalanish O'zbekistonda ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'rgatish sohasida yangi joriy etilgan yondashuvdir. Kahoot va Ibrat Academy kabi vositalar talabalarga grammatika qoidalarini o'yinlar va interaktiv usullar bilan o'rganishga yordam beradi. Ushbu platformalar talabalarni testlar, o'yinlar va turli o'qitish usullari orqali grammatika bilan shug'ullanishlariga imkon beradi. Ushbu maqolada bu platformalardan foydalanib grammatika o'rganishning afzalliklari, qiyinchiliklari va ta'limiy yondashuvlari tahlil qilinadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: grammatika, onlayn platformalar, Kahoot, Ibrat Academy, o'yin asosida o'qitish, test qilish, interaktiv o'qitish.

Grammar is an essential part of language learning. In Uzbekistan, it is common to learn grammar through explicit instructions by combining a grammar-translation method. However, in this quickly-developing technology era, it is highly required to use online platforms as powerful tools to facilitate the grammar learning process. Platforms like Kahoot and Ibrat Academy can introduce a level of interactivity that makes learning grammar more engaging and less boring, especially for learners of English as a Foreign Language (EFL).

Considering previous researches, the use of Kahoot has been considered a positive approach to learning grammar. For example, Musdalifa et al. (2018) stated that students who used Kahoot for learning simple tenses like present simple and past simple showed higher scores in quizzes. Another study by Prawira and Mukhaiyar (2020) looked at high school students using Kahoot. They compared students who used Kahoot with those who learned grammar in a traditional way. The results showed that the students who used Kahoot did much better in grammar tests. In addition to improving test scores, Kahoot has been found to make learning grammar more fun and engaging. According to Hilary et al. (2024), students enjoyed using Kahoot because it turned learning into a game, making grammar lessons less stressful and more exciting. The competitive nature of Kahoot, with quizzes and leaderboards, motivated students to participate more actively in class. This approach helped them stay focused and improve their grammar skills over time.

Considering the Ibrat Academy platform, it uses multiple-choice questions and quizzes to help students engage with grammar rules. The app focuses on many topics and provides students with the opportunity to practice grammar that they have learned. This approach is

particularly effective for learning and using grammar concepts, especially remembering structures. Besides, the app contains a “Friends” icon, which means the students can interact and learn together. Furthermore, the app is free of charge and provides students with the certificate after completing the course.

Drawbacks

Although Kahoot and Ibrat Academy offers many opportunities for language learners, they have some drawbacks to mention. For example, Kahoot might cause anxiety and demotivation among slow-paced learners, as it requires answering questions in a given time. Additionally, the focus on short multiple-choice questions might limit deeper understanding of complex grammar concepts, as it emphasizes quick recall over critical thinking and application. Similarly, the Ibrat Academy app, though beneficial in offering structured grammar practice, also relies heavily on multiple-choice questions. This format may encourage guessing rather than true comprehension. It may not be sufficient for students who need more comprehensive explanations or who benefit from varied question types, like open-ended responses or sentence construction.

Conclusion

In conclusion, both Kahoot and the Ibrat Academy app offer engaging and interactive platforms for teaching grammar, making learning more enjoyable for EFL students. Their game-based approach boosts motivation and participation, helping students improve their grammar skills through immediate feedback and repeated practice. However, the fast-paced nature of Kahoot and the reliance on multiple-choice questions in both platforms can sometimes limit deeper understanding and put pressure on slower learners. Despite these challenges, the overall benefits of increased student engagement and active learning make these tools valuable additions to the grammar classroom.

References:

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